

The Origin of Nautical Cartography: Certitudes, Doubts, and Perplexities

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Abstract

European geographical maps and nautical charts have distinct geneses and underwent separate evolutions. When scientific cartography was reborn in the beginning of the fifteenth century, following the translation and dissemination of Ptolemy's *Geography*, the portolan chart had already been established as an effective navigational tool for over one hundred years. And while new geographical maps started to be constructed by the erudite, using the coordinates and prescriptions given by Ptolemy some thirteen centuries before, charts continued to be made by artisans, on the basis of navigational data collected by pilots. Despite being a unique achievement in the history of cartography, if not in the history of civilization, the creation of the medieval portolan chart was still poorly understood at the turn of the twentieth century. With the introduction of new research tools and a deeper study of the extant sources, we have now reached a situation where the initial state of perplexity concerning the very emergence of the portolan charts has given way to a broad consensus about some central questions. The purpose of this article is to appraise the present state of knowledge regarding the so-called "origins problem".

Keywords: history of cartography; history of navigation; portolan chart; nautical chart; cartometric analysis

1. Introduction

Unlike geographical maps, whose earliest material and textual pieces of evidence date to antiquity, nautical charts are usually considered to have been born in more recent times, during the High Middle Ages. However, no written testimonies have survived containing any useful hints about their origin, and the extant medieval charts, which date from the end of the thirteenth century, are already full-fledged representations of the Mediterranean and Black Sea. Unless we seriously consider that some sort of external hand was involved in the creation of those charts, we are forced to admit that a developmental process of undetermined length took place, and to engage in an educated speculation about its details. Having rejected all theories, old and new, attributing the genesis of nautical cartography to

some pre-medieval civilization, we now have good reasons to consider that charts already existed before the introduction of the magnetic compass in navigation, which occurred near the turn of the twelfth century.

Rather than just proposing or arguing for any theory, the main purpose of this article is to make a point of the situation regarding our present state of knowledge on the so-called *origins problem*. Following the lead of previous researchers, the study is organized around the specific questions of *why*, *how* and *when* nautical cartography was introduced in Europe. Its aim is to be achieved by identifying what I have considered to be the most relevant historiographical questions around the subject and evaluating both the answers proposed so far and the degree of agreement they have gathered.

While clear consensuses seem to have emerged in recent years on some of those issues, other points still raise significant disagreement among scholars. An important example of the first type is the intimate connection, now acknowledged by most historians, between the earliest nautical charts and marine navigation during the Middle Ages. An example of the second group is how the navigational information necessary to construct a chart was acquired, stored, and used for the making of the first prototypes.

The vast extant bibliography, which extends from the late nineteenth century to the present day, testifies to the historiographic importance of the subject and to its popularity among not only well-established historians of cartography but also occasional researchers. Such an interest is mainly justified by two facts: the sudden emergence of the Mediterranean portolan chart into the historical record, more than a century before Ptolemy's *Geography* was translated into Latin; and its unprecedented accuracy and detail, when compared with the contemporaneous cartography. These facts have contributed to covering the subject with a veil of mystery, thus raising the interest of many and triggering the proposal of a number of theories regarding the origin of nautical cartography.

2. Setting the Scene

2.1 Selected state of the art

Among the hundreds of titles that were published since the pioneering study of Nordenskjöld (1897), two influential works of the last century shape the historiography around the origins problem: the chapter of Tony Campbell included in the *History of Cartography* series (Campbell, 1987) and the book of Ramon Pujades, published twenty years later (Pujades, 2007). More recently, the contribution of Tony Campbell has been extended as to include detailed discussions around related subjects such as the date of early charts, cartographic innovations, the representation of navigational hazards, toponymy, and the conventional shapes of islands (Campbell, 2021). These later articles raise fundamental questions not addressed in the former work, and some of the doubts and reserves expressed by Campbell in 1987 have been dropped, following the advancements made in the discipline during the last decades. Two good examples are the navigational purpose of

the early charts and the assumption that they were constructed on navigational data. Especially important for the present study is Campbell's (2021-2023) recent essay about how the mental maps kept by pilots since antiquity may have given birth to the first nautical representations of the Mediterranean Sea, which will be discussed here.

To the hefty works of Campbell and Pujades, two original contributions contemporary to Campbell's chapter should be mentioned because of their pioneering approach and influence on the advancements made in the following decades. Those are the monograph of Jonathan Lanman (1987) and the doctoral thesis of Scott Loomer (1987). While Lanman explored the possibility that the first portolan charts were constructed using the directions and distances contained in the medieval sailing directions, the *portolani*, and acknowledged the effect of magnetic declination on their geometry, Loomer considered that the charts were based on loxodromic compass bearings, rather than distances, and suggested that some form of triangulation was used. This author further concluded, based on paleomagnetic measurements at Mount Etna only, that there was no indication that the tilt affecting all charts up to about 1600 was related to magnetic declination. Thirty-five years after these important contributions, Lanman's idea that portolan charts might have been made with the information contained in portolani seems to have been abandoned, and the conclusion of Loomer that the tilt of charts could not have been caused by magnetic declination is denied by what is known about the spatial distribution of geomagnetic parameters in ancient times.

These two pioneering works were later followed by my own contributions in the fields of cartometric analysis and numerical modeling, applied to the study of medieval and early modern charts (Gaspar, 2008, 2010). Taking profit of the availability of geomagnetic models capable of estimating the spatial distribution of magnetic declination in ancient times, I was able to establish a meaningful connection between the geometry of the early portolan charts and the use of compass directions and estimated distances in their construction. More specifically, I have shown that the gross geometric features of the charts are well explained by the use of uncorrected courses and estimated distances in their construction. This subject will be revisited in the present article when discussing *how* portolan charts were made.

A lengthier word is due about the theory proposed by Roel Nicolai in his doctoral dissertation (Nicolai, 2014), not only because the subject is central to the present study, but also due to its wide dissemination among the community of historians. After its acceptance, the dissertation was brought to the attention of the media and soon followed by an article in a leading journal specialized in the History of Science, a book by a major publisher, and other smaller articles (Nicolai, 2015a, 2015b, 2016b). Making use of his technical knowledge as a professional geodesist, Nicolai concluded that portolan charts could not have been conceived in the Middle Ages, having probably been copied from older regional maps made by an older civilization, acquainted with advanced geodetic and cartographic techniques. In his study, the author reached two provocative conclusions: that the earliest portolan charts are piecewise constructions of regional maps based on geodetic data and adopting the Mercator projection; and that medieval navigation and technology cannot explain their

remarkable planimetric accuracy. Despite the wide dissemination of Nicolai's work, the reaction of the historians was muted. The few published assessments focused on his negative conclusion that portolan charts could not have been conceived in the Middle Ages, mostly ignoring his cartometric approach and the assumptions made to reach such a conclusion (Campbell & Gaspar, 2015; Cormak, 2019; Campbell, 2021-2023).

Except for my own short review, I'm not aware of any other critique of his quantitative methods, which probably reflects the heavy mathematical component of the study. My general interpretation, already expressed in that review, is that Nicolai's approach to the subject appears to be negatively affected by a strong preconception about an ancient origin for portolan charts. By suggesting that they were based on maps produced by a higher and older technology, Nicolai is replacing the consensual theory of a medieval origin with an apparently *ad-hoc* one, without providing a single piece of positive evidence.

The biased arguments and conclusions of Roel Nicolai do not diminish, in my opinion, the effectiveness of a quantitative approach to the origins problem, which has already proved to contain an enormous potential. As I have previously noted, though, "mathematical methods are not magical boxes from which historical truth can be read, as conclusions derived from quantitative analysis and modelling techniques must be carefully scrutinized and validated by historical evidence and common sense. That doesn't seem to have been always the case in this author's contributions, where some prejudiced assumptions and conclusions are detrimental to an otherwise thorough and careful work" (Gaspar, 2015). I will come back to the details of Nicolai's cartometric study in 'Roel Nicolai's thesis'.

2.2 The oldest charts

The Carte Pisane, drawn by an anonymous Italian chart maker near the end of the thirteenth century, is the oldest known nautical chart that has survived to the present day. A recent radiocarbon analysis of the parchment concluded that the animal whose skin was used in the manuscript might have died between 1170 and 1270 (95% confidence), with 1245 as the most probable date (Hofmann *et al.*, 2016). The inconsistency of these dates with the presence of *Palamós*, a town in the eastern coast of Spain that was founded only in 1279, led the historians to accept a *terminus post quem* dating of 1279 (Pujades 2013, 19). This date was later challenged by the fact that a *villa* already existed at the same place before the town was officially founded, about whose existence pilots were certainly aware. This and other similar doubts led Tony Campbell to revise the dating of the chart to ca. 1270, thus bringing it into line with the results of the radiocarbon analysis (Campbell, 2020). From the results of a recent hyperspectral analysis of the manuscript, the possibility of the chart being a palimpsest was rejected, as no traces were found of a previous use of the skin.¹

The chart originally represented the Mediterranean and Black Seas, together with part of the Atlantic coasts of Europe, including a crude depiction of Great Britain. The manuscript is

¹ The hyperspectral analysis of the manuscript was made in 2019, in Paris, following a proposal of project Medea-Chart. The results, which haven't revealed any surprises, were made available by the Laboratoire de restauration des musées de France, together with those of the radiocarbon dating and pigment analysis: <https://merovingio.c2rmf.cnrs.fr/pisane/> (Retrieved January 2023).

in a bad state of conservation, showing the effects of aging and the exposure to light, water, and dirt. Most of the area representing the Black Sea was torn and removed (part of it during a restoration made in the nineteenth century), the original colours have faded and some place names are barely visible. However, the representation of the Mediterranean Sea is remarkably accurate when compared with the medieval traditional cartography.

Three other early charts have survived from the last decade of the thirteenth and the beginning of the fourteenth centuries: the Cortona chart (ca. 1300), which may originally have depicted the Mediterranean, Black Sea and west coasts of Europe, but is now truncated on its western part; the Avignon chart (ca. 1300), from which only a fragment survived depicting the western Mediterranean and part of the coasts of France and Britain; and the Lucca chart (ca. 1310).² These were followed by the charts and atlases produced by Pietro and Perrino Vesconte in Venice, between 1311 and 1327, where most of the cartographic conventions that characterize early nautical cartography consolidated, and improvements were introduced in the depiction of the Adriatic Sea and Atlantic coasts of Europe.

2.3 The *Liber de existencia riveriarum*

The *Liber de existencia riveriarum et forma maris nostri mediterranei* is a Latin manuscript written at the beginning of the thirteenth century, probably by a cleric in Pisa. Because of its apparent reference to a map and the compelling evidence that a primitive nautical chart may have been used in its preparation, this text is of paramount importance for the origins problem. According to its anonymous author, the purpose of the work was to describe the Mediterranean Sea in *writing*, according to the way places were situated in the world relative to the winds, that is, to geographical directions. Although it was first revealed in 1944, by Roberto Almagià, the manuscript remained forgotten for half a century, until Patrick Gautier-Dalché published a detailed study, in 1995, containing the transcription of the Latin text and a partial translation of its Prologue (Gautier-Dalché, 1995). The period between 1160 and 1200, first suggested by this author for its completion, was later corrected to after 1204, by Ramón Pujades (2007, 519, note 76). Due to the inclusion of the Black Sea in the manuscript, Pujades argued it could not have been prepared before the fall of Constantinople to the Venetians, in 1204.

The work starts with a geographical summary consisting of a list of 159 tracks connecting, in a continuous way, a series of places around the margins of the Mediterranean Sea, for which the corresponding distances are given. In 23 of these tracks, mostly between faraway places, both distances and directions are provided. After the Prologue, where the author refers to the context and purpose of the work, and reveals his sources, a portolan-like text follows. It consists of a systematic description of the coasts of the Mediterranean, Black Sea, western Europe and northwest Africa, organized in 45 regional sections, each introduced by a short geographical account of the region, followed by a systematic list of distances

² Some recent bibliography about these three charts is mentioned in Gaspar (2019, note 19). For details and images of these early charts, see the Medea-Chart database: <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/50>, <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/54>, <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/358>.

between adjacent places. These are complemented by some tracks connecting a place on the coast to an island or to another place in a different region. Although we can infer, from the words of the author, that the text was not intended for the use of pilots, most part of the information reveals a nautical origin: directions are expressed in a system of 16 winds (which is explained in the text), and explicit mentions are made to nautical sources. Based on a reference to a map or chart (*cartula mappa mundi*) that the author had the intention to prepare (or had already prepared, according to some authors), both Gautier-Dalché (1995, Ch. 2) and Pujades (2007, 513) considered the *Liber de existencia riveriarum* to represent convincing evidence that nautical charts were being produced at the dawn of the thirteenth century.

2.4 Magnetic declination

Magnetic declination is the horizontal angle between the direction of geographical North and the direction of a magnetic compass free of influences other than the Earth's magnetic field. Magnetic declination varies both spatially and secularly and may reach values of 90° or more near the magnetic poles. During the Middle Ages and early modern period, from about year 1000 onward, magnetic declination in the Mediterranean Sea reached maximum values of about +12° in the central Mediterranean and Adriatic Sea, then steadily decreasing to about 0° near 1600, before inverting sign and increasing again (Fig. 1). The earliest written references to the *variation* of magnetic compasses (that is, to the differences to true geographical directions) are in the diary of Cristopher Columbus, for 11 and 17 September 1492, during his first voyage to the Caribbean Sea (Heathcote, 1932, 83). Considering the word used by him to designate the western variation of the compass (*noruestear*), it is very likely that the phenomenon had been known for some time by the Portuguese pilots, with whom Columbus worked together before his mission. In a text probably still written in the fifteenth century, the Portuguese pilot João de Lisboa complained how some mariners were rotating the compass roses over the magnetized needles so that they indicated the true North at the region where they were being used. This practise, which was justified by alleged defects in the making of the instruments, was strongly criticized by the pilot (Albuquerque, 1982, 14).

It is very unlikely that the medieval mariners of the Mediterranean were aware of the phenomenon of magnetic declination, even after the introduction of the marine compass, during the last decades of the twelfth century. Although the variations of the magnetized needles may have been detected, by comparing the compass North with the direction of the Pole Star, the differences were relatively small, considering the poor precision and accuracy of the extant compasses (and thus, their poor accuracy), and varied from place to place and with the orientation of Ursa Minor in the sky. More difficult to explain is why the average tilt of the portolan charts up the end of the sixteenth century (see Fig. 1) remained

approximately constant despite the regular decrease of magnetic declination in the Mediterranean and Black Seas.³

Figure 1 – Secular variation of magnetic declination in the Mediterranean and Black Seas, from 1150 to 1600, calculated by the Korte & Constable (2005) geomagnetic model CALS7k2 (coloured lines). The blue circles represent the tilt of a series of about 80 portolan charts from 1270 to 1600, as estimated from the orientation of the line connecting Gibraltar to Antioch.

When Tony Campbell wrote his chapter in the *History of Cartography* (Campbell, 1987), the knowledge about the spatial distribution of magnetic declination in the Mediterranean and Black Seas, during the Middle Ages, was extremely sparse, being limited to a couple of values deduced from the examination of solidified lava flows in the Italian Peninsula. We know how this lack of information have influenced the conclusions drawn about how portolan charts were made, not only by Campbell, but also by Lanman and Loomer. While Campbell remained extremely cautious about the use of navigational data and how magnetic declination might have affected the geometry of the early charts, Lanman and Loomer were both driven, by the lack of sufficient data, to partially wrong conclusions. This situation changed dramatically when directional geomagnetic data for the whole world, obtained from the analysis of lake sediments, archaeomagnetic artefacts and solidified lava flows, were used to construct models capable of estimating magnetic declination in ancient times (Korte & Constable, 2005; Korte, Genevay *et al.*, 2005). Although the output of these models may be affected by errors of a couple of degrees, mostly due to lack of data in some regions or epochs, they have literally changed the historiography of portolan charts, as they

³ In fact, there is a slight negative trend in the tilt of charts between ca. 1310 and before 1600. Its likely explanation is the progressive correction of a northward displacement of the eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea, which mostly affects the older charts. See, below, 'The Sub-chart Theory'.

shed an important light onto such critical issues as the date of the earliest charts and how they were constructed. The suggestion of Tony Campbell that the value of magnetic declination deduced from the local distortions of the charts could be used to date the earliest prototypes can finally be concretized. The main reason is that charts were not updated regularly with more recent navigational data, and the patterns kept as models in the workshops could have been used for many decades without major improvements. As I have suggested in a previous article (Gaspar, 2008), it is possible that the Mediterranean pilots may have resorted to an *ad hoc* solution to the mismatch between the compass and the charts (when it started to be noticed), by manipulating the instruments, as Portuguese mariners subsequently did. The same kind of cartographic inertia occurred much later in the nautical cartography following the Cantino planisphere (1502), where the eastward displacement and stretching of Africa caused by the effect of magnetic declination was kept approximately constant on Portuguese charts up to the seventeenth century, despite the latter's significant variation (Gaspar, 2013).

3. Why?

Nautical charts of all periods share three main interconnected functions in navigation. Firstly, they are repositories of information, both general and strictly navigational. This information is provided both in graphical (coastlines, shoals, flags indicating possession, etc.) and in textual form (legends, place names, etc.). Secondly, they serve as planning tools, e.g., to prepare voyages. Using a pair of compasses, charts are used to measure directions and distances between places, and to decide the best routes. Thirdly, they are used to control, and sometimes to register, the position of the ship. This can be done by simply comparing the content of a chart with the lands the pilot can see along the way or, when the coast is not in sight, by using it to graphically determine the position of the ship based on the course steered and the distance made, i.e., by *dead reckoning*. The earliest extant written description of how charts could be used in navigation is in Benedetto Cotrugli's *De Navigazione* (1464-1465). It is there explained how to fix the ship's position by observing conspicuous features on land, and how to register that position on the chart with a drop of wax. Whether this kind of practise was common or not is unknown, as no traces of such wax marks have so far been found.⁴ Identical doubts apply to the process known as *toleta de marteloio*, proposed by the Venetian chart maker Andrea Bianco in his atlas of 1436 (but likely used earlier), intended to determine the position of the ship and compensate for deviations in the intended route.⁵

⁴ In fact, this procedure would probably be unfeasible using the portolan charts that survived to our days, due to their small scale. Cotrugli wrote his *De Navigazione* for the Venetian Senate, with the purpose of composing a treatise on navigation. The original was lost but two copies are extant: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, MS 557 and Lawrence J. Schoenberg Collection MS LJS 473 (Falchetta, 2009). A commented excerpt of the parts dealing with the navigational chart is in Almeida (2022, pp. 53-60).

⁵ The process aims to solve, using a table or diagram, the right triangles associated with the track of a ship at sea and the deviations from the planned course. Solutions are provided for the eight classical rhumbs, separated by one point ($11\frac{1}{4}^\circ$).

3.1 The intimate connection between early nautical charts and navigation

It is now accepted by most historians that the medieval nautical chart was conceived and constructed as an instrument for navigation. This interpretation, which may appear as a tautology to the present-day reader, did not seem to gather a unanimous consensus when the first volumes of the *History of Cartography* were published. According to Felipe Fernández-Armesto (2007, 749),

The history of the development of the sea chart is so obscure that we cannot even be sure that this type of document was developed for mariner's purposes; it may have been a visual aid to illustrate – for the enlightenment of passengers, landlubbers, and such interested parties as merchants – the data pilots preferred to carry in their heads or rutters.

This radical statement, which was already controversial at the time it was expressed, can no longer be taken seriously. In fact, as Tony Campbell had already pointed out in 1987, the evidence that nautical charts were used on board by the Mediterranean pilots is overwhelming.⁶ It is also known, from the extensive documentary evidence provided by Ramon Pujades (2007, pp. 428-439), that charts were taken aboard most ships during the fourteenth century, together with other instruments of navigation. In some cases, such as in the city of Genoa, the private activity of chart making became a monopoly controlled by the state authorities (Astengo, 2007, 209).

On the other hand, the abundant navigational information provided by the earliest extant charts, which includes the depiction of hazards located far from land, leaves no doubts about their purpose. When we compare the oldest exemplars, such as the *Carte Pisane* (ca. 1270), with a present-day nautical chart, we realize that they share a number of features which are indispensable to the practice of navigation: they are drawn to scale, they exhibit a distance scale, they respect geographical directions, and they depict specific information necessary for planning and conducting navigation. Moreover, most of the information is usually concentrated along the coastlines (prominent features, place names) and at some locations at sea (islets, navigational hazards), in such a way as to leave the wet areas as free of text as possible. Both in the oldest and present-day navigational charts, the inland areas are usually left almost blank. These coincidences seem to imply that at least the most basic navigational functionalities are shared by the old and the modern charts, namely, to retrieve information necessary to plan and conduct navigation, to measure distances and directions between places, and to control the position of the ship along the way.

An important implication of the intimate connection between portolan charts and the practice of navigation is that any attempt to understand how they were made and used must consider the fact that they were conceived as *instruments for navigation* and constructed using navigational data.⁷ These facts do not imply, however, that those charts were made and used for navigation *only* and that pilots *always* used them at sea.

⁶ As noted by Tony Campbell, by the end of the fourteenth century several Mediterranean maritime authorities had decreed that every ship must carry at least two charts on board (Campbell, 1987, 439-40).

⁷ This subject will be addressed below, when discussing *how* the charts were made.

It is, indeed, a well-known fact that nautical charts were also produced with purposes not related to navigation, and that some workshops were exclusively committed to it. The earliest known examples are probably some of the atlases produced by Pietro Vesconte between 1313 and 1321, exhibiting a kind of decoration more typical of erudite publications, which would be superfluous in purely nautical charts. *Mutatis mutandis*, the apparent non-navigational purpose of an old nautical chart, suggested by its decorative features, does not necessarily imply that it could not be (and was not) used at sea. Comparisons made between decorated and non-decorated charts make it evident that both types shared the same cartographic standards, concerning scale and the geometry of the geographical features, which imply that they were copied from the same patterns. A few highly decorated charts are extant, one of them of the end of the fifteenth century, exhibiting marks of navigational use.⁸ Later examples of nautical cartography obviously not produced for navigation, owing to the small size of the charts, are the about one hundred atlases of the Venetian cartographer Battista Agnese and those of his disciple Francesco Ghisolfi.

3.2 The use of charts in navigation

Coming back to the comparison between old and present-day nautical charts, a fundamental difference with obvious implications in the way they could be used in navigation should be stressed. That is the relatively small scale of the portolan charts, when compared to the present-day nautical charts, preventing them from being used effectively near the coast, due to the lack of detail. This applies not only to charts covering the whole Mediterranean Sea, but also to those included in portolan atlases (most of them traced from general charts), whose scale is of the order of 1:5 million (that is, 1 cm to 50 km). An important conclusion that can be reached from this limitation is that portolan charts were mainly used for planning and executing long-range navigation and, when closer to land, visually controlling the position of the ship. Interestingly, this is the kind of use smaller boats make of printed nautical charts today.

This brings us back to the question raised above, whether pilots *always* used charts to navigate in the Mediterranean Sea or not. On this matter we should make the difference between coastal navigation in relatively small areas, often made by local pilots who could rely on their knowledge and experience, and long-range sailing. In the latter case, the emergence of the nautical chart provided the pilots with a powerful tool for planning and executing their trips, most especially in less familiar regions, and when unfavorable conditions required a change of route. Exactly how, by whom and in what circumstances, charts were used to plan and execute navigation in the Mediterranean waters remains unknown.

⁸ That is the signed and dated chart of the Portuguese cartographer Jorge de Aguiar (1492). See Gaspar and Krtalić (2023, Ch. 11) and the Medea-Chart database: <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/4>.

4. When?

To avoid ambiguity, a distinction will be made from now on between the charts that were produced according to the model of the *Carte Pisane*, that is, those based on compass courses and exhibiting compass roses of 32 winds (to which corresponds a precision of $11\frac{1}{4}^\circ$), and the primitive charts suggested by the text and data of the *Liber de existencia riveriarum*, based on astronomical directions and with a system of only 16 directions, corresponding to a precision of $22\frac{1}{2}^\circ$. We will continue to designate the former as *portolan charts*, reserving the term *proto-portolan charts* for the latter.

4.1 The date of the earliest portolan charts

Surprisingly, this issue is relatively easy to clarify if we accept that the earliest portolan charts were constructed on uncorrected magnetic directions given by the marine compass. The earliest known mentions to the use of magnetic compasses in navigation are those contained in the Latin texts of Alexander Neckam (1157–1217), which date from about 1190 (Thomas Wright, 1857, 1863). The instrument described in those texts is a primitive one, consisting of a magnetic needle floating in a bowl of water. According to Neckam, the devices were used when the sky was clouded, preventing the observation of the Sun and stars. Nothing indicates in the text that they were absolute novelties or that their use was rare. On the contrary, it is suggested that bringing them on board was highly recommended, if not mandatory.⁹ This is consistent with the majority of the directional data contained in the *Liber*, whose systematic errors agree well with the average value of magnetic declination in the central Mediterranean, as of 1200. In short, the use of magnetic compasses in navigation by the turn of the century was already established in the region. Whether those primitive floating compasses immediately triggered the production of nautical charts based on compass directions is difficult to say. If that were the case, then the accuracy of those earlier charts must have been much poorer than that of the *Carte Pisane*. A major improvement was the invention of the dry pivoted compass, described by Pierre de Maricourt (Peter Peregrinus) in 1256 (Pierre, 1904, pp. 38-39). Although this particular instrument, graduated in degrees, was intended for astronomical use, similar models were probably made for nautical use. This may explain the higher accuracy of the directions in the *Carte Pisane* and *Compasso de Navegare*¹⁰, one of the earliest known portolani, when compared with the sixteen wind directions of the *Liber de existencia riveriarum*.

Based on the apparent absence of information copied from a nautical chart in al-Idrisi's *Tabula Rogeriana*, Tony Campbell (2021-2023, 'H.2e. The Charta Rogeriana...') postulated a *terminus post quem* date of 1154 for the earliest prototypes. I agree with this conclusion

⁹ That is not the opinion of Tony Campbell (personal communication), who considers that the reason Neckam referred to those devices was *because* they were novel. On this point, we may argue that their use would only have come to the knowledge of Neckam, an English cleric working far from Italy, if they were relatively ubiquitous by the time. In fact, he may have known about the floating compass while he was teaching in Paris, before 1186 (Beazley, 1911).

¹⁰ The *Compasso de Navegare* is preserved in the Staatsbibliothek, Berlin (MS Hamilton 396) and bears the date of 1296. Based in its content, Motzo (1947) considers the manuscript to be an updated copy of an older original, made before 1256.

because, if minimally accurate nautical charts existed at the time, the representation of (at least) the northern shores of the Mediterranean would not appear so crude as on al-Idrisi's map. This consideration applies both to charts based on compass directions and to the proto-portolan charts suggested by the data contained in the *Liber*. Concerning the first type, more specifically the charts based on a system of 32 winds, three factors should be taken into consideration for establishing a *terminus post quem*: the date of the *Liber* (after 1205), the development of the marine compass, and the tilt of the earliest extant charts.

Because all directions contained in the *Liber* are referred to a system of 16 winds, it is unlikely that charts based on a system of 32 winds, like the Carte Pisane, were available at the time. If that were the case, and because those charts were probably produced not far from the place where the manuscript was written (Pisa), its author would most likely be aware of their existence and would have used the updated information to prepare his work. It is thus reasonable to infer that, by the time the manuscript was finished, they did not exist. As for the development of improved compasses, with a precision of at least $11\frac{1}{4}^\circ$, all we know is that they already existed by the time Pierre de Maricourt wrote his letter, in 1256. It may well be that a nautical version graduated in points (instead of degrees) had been developed some time ago and was already in use. Rather than concluding, as Nicolai (2014, 150), that the Carte Pisane could not have been made on compass directions because the instruments of the time were not accurate enough, we should invert the argument. In the presence of compelling evidence that the earliest charts were constructed using compass directions, we should conclude, on the contrary, that accurate enough instruments were available at the time.

Figure 2 – Variation of the chart tilt in the western Mediterranean, as estimated from the orientation of the line between Cape Gata and Cape Passero, in charts between ca. 1270 and 1510 (red circles), compared with the variation of the average magnetic declination along the same path (dashed line).

The red circles in Fig. 2 represent the tilt in the western Mediterranean on charts between ca. 1270 and 1510, as estimated from the orientation of the line connecting Cape Gata (southern Spain) to Cape Passero (southeast tip of Sicily), compared with the secular

variation of the average magnetic declination along the same line.¹¹ The purpose of this graph is to estimate the date of the prototype, or prototypes, from which the earliest extant portolan charts may have derived, under the assumption that they were indeed constructed with uncorrected compass directions. The significant dispersion of the data, with a range of about two degrees, is not easy to interpret. Because most charts were copied from the available patterns, we would expect less variability. Two main reasons may explain the apparent anomaly: the less-than-perfect copying processes and the distortion of the parchments due to aging.

Special attention should be given to the period between ca. 1270 (Carte Pisane) and 1350, because of the larger dispersion of the data, which may reveal the presence of different lineages. At least two different prototypes may be present: one related to the Carte Pisane, comprising the eight charts with tilts larger than eight degrees; and the other comprising the remaining six charts, with tilts equal to or less than eight degrees (see Table 1). If this interpretation is correct, then these prototypes may have been created using navigational data collected at two separate occasions: the first between ca. 1220 and ca. 1260, and the second, after 1280. Apparently, most charts produced after 1350 were based on this second prototype. Three exceptions are the charts by Francesco de Cesanis (1421), Bartolomeo Pareto (1455), Berenguer Ripol & Jaume Bertran (1456), and one attributed to Judah Abenzara (1505), which may have used one of Vesconte's atlases as a model.

Table 1

Tilts of charts and atlases between c. 1270 and c. 1350

Chart	Date	Archive	Medea-chart ID	Tilt	Prototype
Carte Pisane	c. 1270	BnF	MCC50	9.2	1
Carta Riccardiana	1300-1325	Biblioteca Riccardiana	MCC53	8.6	1
Pietro Vesconte (atlas)	1318	Museo Corer	MCA123	8.9	1
Pietro Vesconte (atlas)	1318	Österreichische Nationalbibliothek	MCA140	8.6	1
Perrino Vesconte (atlas)	1321	Zentralbibliothek Zürich	MCA137	8.8	1
Pietro Vesconte (atlas)	c. 1321	Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon	MCA122	8.0	2
[Pietro Vesconte] (atlas)	c. 1321	British Library	MCA120	8.5	1
[Pietro Vesconte] (atlas)	c. 1321	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana	MCA121	8.5	1
Lucca chart	< 1327	Archivio di Stato di Lucca	MCC358	8.5	1
Carignano chart	c. 1327	Archivio di Stato di Firenze		7.7	2
Angelino Dulceti	1330	Private owner	MCC468	7.0	2
Angelino Dulceti	1339	BnF		7.5	2
[Angelino Dulceti]	1339-1350	British Library	MCC100	8.0	2
Anonymous (Italy)	c. 1350	BnF	MCC431	7.5	2

¹¹ Because of the contamination caused by northward displacement of the eastern Mediterranean, especially in the older charts, it was decided not to use the line connecting Gibraltar to Antioch, as in Fig. 1.

Although these preliminary results should be taken with considerable care, especially regarding the number of prototypes and the extrapolated dates, they seem to confirm the presence of different lineages among the earliest charts, as previously suggested by other researchers, based on stylistic factors and cartographic conventions (Campbell, '2023, N.1b. Not a single lineage'). Further research should enlarge the analysis to different regions of the Mediterranean, permitting the inclusion of early charts not considered here, and also take non-metric features into account.

4.2 The proto-portolan chart

As mentioned above, the earliest known reference to what might be a nautical chart is contained in the Latin manuscript *Liber de existencia riveriarum*, completed in the beginning of the thirteenth century by an anonymous Italian cleric. Recently, I published an article containing a reworked translation of a larger part of its Prologue and a numerical analysis of the directions listed in the manuscript, drawing attention to some points relevant to the present work (Gaspar, 2019). The first concerns the long list of tracks connecting adjacent places along the margins of the Mediterranean. It is not easy to consider that all these data have originated in *direct* navigational information provided by mariners, which could only be collected in planned surveys. Possible alternatives are that they were measured from a map or copied from a text. On the first option, it should be recalled that distances and directions connecting nearby places could not have been read from a typical portolan chart, due to its small scale. On the second, Gautier Dalché (1995, 63) noted some exact agreements with the *Liber de liberatione civitatum orientis*, a book about the first crusade written by the Genovese Caffaro di Caschifellone (ca. 1080 - 1166), and with some sections of al-Idrisi's *Geography* addressing Italy. This agreement, which can hardly be considered a coincidence, may indicate that part of the data utilized by the author of the *Liber* were copied from textual sources.

An apparent anomaly affecting the directions in the *Liber* is how they are negatively correlated with the lengths of the corresponding tracks; that is, the shorter the track the larger the error.¹² This could be explained with the uncertainty over the exact orientation of the line connecting two places on a map, when one or both are located on close-by islands, or their exact locations are unclear. Another relevant feature is how some islands and parts of the coast are described in the text as if they were read from a map, rather than originated in the direct testimony of pilots. Particularly revealing is the presence of long-distance tracks with limited navigational relevance, oriented against the prevailing winds or even intersecting dry land (Gaspar, 2019, p. 8).¹³

¹² This feature also agrees with the results of the analysis made by Roel Nicolai of the data contained in the *Compasso de Navegare*. See Nicolai (2018).

¹³ This anomaly was previously noted by Gautier-Dalché (1995, p. 80) and by Kelley (1995), who justly asked "Could it be that portolani owe more to portolan charts than vice versa?". In a contribution focused on the analysis of the *Compasso de Navegare*, Nicolai (2018, pp. 3, 5, 18) found numerous other instances of "impossible course legs", and echoed Kelley's suggestion that portolans were likely based on data scaled from charts.

All these features suggest that a cartographic representation was used as a source for some of the text's content, one in which directions and distances could be measured using a wind rose of 16 directions and a distance bar: that is, a nautical chart of some sort. An important detail that may shed additional light onto the nature of such a chart is the fact that all directions given in the list of tracks preceding the Prologue are unaffected by any systematic error, which can only mean that they were measured by astronomical means rather than with a marine compass.¹⁴ Concerning the directions included in the body of the text, my analysis has shown that a significant part of them, mainly in the central Mediterranean, are affected by magnetic declination. All this confirms the statement of the author that several sources were used to gather the necessary information and suggests that the *Liber* was written at a time when compass directions were being measured and recorded.

Exactly what looked like the cartographic representation used as a source by the author of the *Liber* is uncertain. The most we can say is that it depicted the whole Mediterranean Sea, was based on a system of 16 winds, was drawn using astronomical directions, contained a scale of miles and showed place names along the coastlines. These features clearly exclude contemporary *mappae-mundi* or geographical maps, like al-Idris's *Tabula Rogeriana*; not only because of their non-nautical conventions but also due to their much inferior accuracy. How that primitive nautical chart related to the prototypes from which the earliest extant portolan charts were copied is difficult to say. But it seems reasonable to assume that some of the information contained in this cartographic model could easily be imported to a new one, based on compass directions.¹⁵

5. How?

A broad consensus has been reached among historians that portolan charts, not only were conceived for the purpose of navigation, but also were made on navigational data collected by pilots. Exactly what kind of data, and how they were used to draw the charts, has been the subject of a long discussion since before Tony Campbell's chapter in the *History of Cartography* (1987). Almost unanimous is that the main cause for the tilt of all portolan charts, which was to persist up to the seventeenth century, was magnetic declination. On this matter, significant advances were made in the last decades owing to the emergence of geomagnetic models capable of estimating magnetic declination in ancient times, as well as the development of novel numerical techniques that permitted the geometric features of the old charts to be assessed and modelled, simulating the methods supposedly used to construct them. In this section, three related subjects will be dealt with: the construction of

¹⁴ That is, by observing the Sun and stars (especially the Pole Star) at the moments when their geographic directions had been previously tabulated by the astronomers, such as culminations, risings and settings. See Gaspar (2019, 10-11).

¹⁵ This is a difficult question, whose clarification should take two related facts into account: the major differences between the toponymic sequences in the *Liber*, *Compasso de Navegare* and *Carte Pisane* (Campbell, 2011, 'Toponymic Transmission Before 1311 ['Precursor Names']'); and the compelling evidence that the earliest known portolan charts (or, more precisely, their prototypes) may have been made as piecewise assemblages of regional charts. See below, 'The Sub-chart Theory')

a nautical chart using navigational data; the sub-chart hypothesis, according to which the first portolan chart covering the whole traditional area was a piecewise assemblage of regional representations; and how navigational information was stored before the construction of that chart.

5.1 The making of the charts

The idea that portolan charts were constructed using compass directions and estimated distances collected by the pilots seems to be implicit in the interpretations of many historians since at least Nordenskjöld, although few of them went to the point of giving details about the process (Campbell, 1987, 384-388). The main problem with this natural interpretation is that no explicit textual evidence is extant describing the construction process before the sixteenth century, leaving the very charts as the only available primary sources. A popular version among researchers of the past is that the geometrical structure of the earliest prototypes consisted in some form of triangular network connecting conspicuous points in the Mediterranean basin. That was the suggestion of Loomer (1987, 146), who considered that the network was calculated by measuring the internal angles of the triangles and, more recently, is implicit in the thesis of Nicolai (2014), that portolan charts were copied from older maps constructed on geodetic data. In both cases, magnetic declination would have no effect on the values of the internal angles of the triangles, whatever the method they used to measure them. That is one of the reasons why both Loomer and Nicolai considered that the tilt of portolan charts was not caused by magnetic declination.¹⁶ For Tony Campbell (2021-2023, '1.1. Inadvertent Triangulation'), the network consisted in a set of paths connecting prominent places, like capes and major ports, whose orientations and lengths were measured by pilots in their voyages, and then memorized as mental maps. This information, which may have been kept and added over centuries, was then used to construct the earliest prototypes. An alternative process, first suggested by Waldo Tobler (1977, 51-64), would consist in measuring a large number of distances across the Mediterranean, and then iteratively adjust some initial positions of the end points on a plane, in such a way as to respect as accurately as possible the distances between them.¹⁷

In my PhD dissertation (Gaspar, 2010, pp. 73-84), I have generalized Tobler's idea, as to also include the geographical orientations of the tracks, in the presence of magnetic declination. Three adjustable parameters were introduced in the model, aiming to replicate as realistically as possible the conditions and processes of the medieval cartographers: the spatial distribution of magnetic declination for various dates; a maximum allowed distance between points; and a variable weighting factor given to distances and directions used as

¹⁶ Loomer (1987, 167) suggested that the tilt of the charts was a side effect of the triangulation scheme, while Nicolai (2014) considered that the sub-charts used to construct the representation of the Mediterranean and Black Sea were made using geodetical data and the Mercator projection.

¹⁷ The idea is easy to understand if we imagine that one wants to determine the relative positions of a number of cities in a country, knowing only the distances between them. This is what is called *multidimensional scaling* in social sciences, a process equivalent to the *least square adjustment* used in Geodesy and many other disciplines.

input data.¹⁸ Figure 3 shows the output of my Empirical Map Projection (EMP) model for two extreme conditions, not considering the effect of magnetic declination: only distances, as in Tobler's model (left); and only directions (right). While the first output is identical to the one obtained by Tobler, the second is identical to a Mercator projection. This second output much weakens the thesis, proposed by various authors, that the Mercator projection was *explicitly* adopted in the construction of the first portolan charts. As remarked by Loomer (1987, 166-167), and demonstrated by my numerical model, a Mercator representation is *automatically* obtained when loxodromic tracks are used to construct a chart. Fig. 4 shows the output produced by the EMP model when a weight of 80% is given to directions (and 20% to distances), a maximum allowed distance of 30° is considered (about 3 300 km), and all directions are affected by magnetic declination as of 1200. Fig. 5 shows the geographical grid of meridians and parallels implicit in an old portolan chart, the one drawn by Angelino Dulceti in 1339.¹⁹

Figure 3 – Two outputs of the EMP model using loxodromic tracks as input: only distances (left) and only directions (right). The grid on the right is undistinguishable from a Mercator projection.

¹⁸ These parameters were then fine-tuned in successive runs of the model until the resulting grid of meridians and parallels became as close as possible to the ones implicit in the old nautical charts. Establishing a maximum distance is justified by the fact that few trips would have been made across exceptionally large distances in the Mediterranean, without a scale. The inclusion of a weighting factor aimed to better identify the actual data used to construct the charts. I concluded that a large preference (80%) was given to directions over distances (20%), which is a reasonable and expected result, considering that mariners must have trusted more the courses measured by the magnetic compasses than the estimated distances.

¹⁹ This grid can be estimated from a set of points of known present day latitudes and longitudes, positively identified in the old chart and a modern map. The numerical process was facilitated by the use of MapAnalyst, a computer application designed for the purpose of comparing maps, freely available on the internet: <https://mapanalyst.org/>.

Figure 4 – Outputs of the EMP model working with loxodromic tracks, when a larger weight (80%) is given to distances over directions (20%), the maximum allowed distance is 30° and magnetic declination as of 1200 is considered.

A detailed comparison of the two representations has been made in a previous article (Gaspar, 2008). Here, I only want to draw the attention to the fact that the gross geometric features of Dulceti's chart were well reproduced by the model, namely: the average tilt of the Mediterranean basin, the approximate ratio between the length of the parallel and meridian segments; and the slight convergence of meridians.²⁰ This result demonstrates that the actual geometry of the portolan charts (here represented by an early exemplar) is well explained by the usage of uncorrected compass directions and estimated distances in their construction, and that a much larger weight was given to the directions over the distances.²¹ An important feature not reproduced by the model is the scale exaggeration of the eastern part of Dulceti's chart (namely the Aegean Sea and the Black Sea), which is apparent in the comparison between the size of the geographical quadrilaterals, and in the larger slope of the parallels in the Eastern Mediterranean and Black Seas. This feature, which has been noticed by various researchers, is addressed next, when discussing the sub-chart hypothesis.

5.2 The sub-chart hypothesis

The idea that the earliest prototypes may have been constructed as a piecewise assemblage of regional charts has been proposed by many researchers, who based their various hypotheses on the regional scale and orientation variations affecting most portolan charts. Early supporters of the theory were Herman Wagner (1895), Nordenskiöld (1897) and Konrad Kretschmer (1909), later followed by James Kelly Jr. (1977), David Woodward (1987) and Scott Loomer (Campbell, 1987, 383-384; 2023, 54-58 and Loomer, 1987, 159-165).

²⁰ It is important to remark that the slight convergence of the meridians in the old chart is explained by the usage of distances in its construction. Such convergence would be absent if only directions had been used.

²¹ Indeed, even a medieval navigator would have given much more weight to compass directions than to estimated distances, due to the uncertainty associated with the latter. That is the reason why, following the introduction of latitude measurements in navigation, in the last decades of the fifteenth century, positions at sea started to be determined using observed latitudes and compass directions, rather than latitudes and distances.

Figure 5 – Geographical grid implicit to the chart of Angelino Dulceti (1339), estimated using the known coordinates of a sample of control points (red circles). The grid was cropped on the margins to avoid extrapolation beyond the area covered by the control points.

More recently, Roel Nicolai (2014, 261-262, 268-270) performed a detailed cartometric analysis of five portolan charts made between ca. 1270 (carte Pisane) and 1466 (Petrus Roselli) and tentatively concluded, based on scale and tilt variations, that they were the result of assembling eight regional representations: two for the Atlantic coasts of Europe and Africa, four for the Mediterranean, and one for the Black Sea and the Sea of Marmara. The proposed explanation for the anomalies, which would be otherwise incompatible with his thesis that all regional parts were based on advanced geodesic data, was the mistakes introduced by the medieval chart makers when stitching the various parts together.²² The numerical approach of Nicolai is commented in more detail below, in 'Roel Nicolai's thesis'.

In a recent essay, the idea that the first chart depicting the Mediterranean was an assemblage of regional representations was strongly opposed by Tony Campbell. For this author,

The sub-chart thesis ... is a theoretical, quasi—mathematical and surely anachronistic solution to what appears to be an imaginary problem. It imposes arbitrary boundaries across the featureless sea, in wilful dismissal of the routes sailors were routinely taking ... The main weaknesses of the sub-chart theory ... is that it posits a number of regionally focused efforts, presumably aimed at local needs, somehow morphing into what was totally different, and wholly unprecedented, namely a universal picture of – to a medieval sailor – their entire world. (Campbell, 2021-2023, 'The Sub-Chart Hypothesis')

²² See Nicolai (2016, pp. 8-11). As previously noted, the author's explanation for the tilt affecting all portolan charts up to ca. 1600 was that it was introduced by the same map makers to make the resulting chart agree with the compass directions.

However emphatic these arguments may appear, Campbell's conviction seems contradicted by what appears to be undeniable geometric evidence. The different proposals of different authors about the coverage of each sub-chart, which he seems to take as a weak point of the theory, are nothing more than different interpretations of the same complex geometric evidence. The arguments of Ramon Pujades against the theory, which Campbell partially reproduces in his essay, are mainly centered on the lack of any traces, direct or indirect, supporting the existence of those sub-charts. Once again, and unless alternative explanations are provided for the strong geometric evidence provided by the extant charts, the hypothesis remains valid.

In more recent unpublished research, where those variations were illustrated using the concept of "error signature", I could identify, not only to the variations in tilt and scale, but also to the marks left on charts by the stitching process. Fig. 6 illustrates the variation of the apparent latitude errors with the longitude, across the Mediterranean, Black Sea and Atlantic coasts of Europe and Africa, in the chart of Mecia de Viladestes.²³ Notice the presence of three well-defined clusters of data with different average trends, which are directly related to the tilt of the chart in those regions: the Atlantic Ocean; the western and central Mediterranean, and the Adriatic Sea; and the eastern Mediterranean, Aegean Sea and Black Sea.

Figure 6 - Variation of the apparent latitude errors with longitude, in the chart of Mecia de Viladestes (1413). At least three clusters of data are identifiable, each with different trends: the Atlantic Ocean; the western and central Mediterranean, and the Adriatic Sea; and the eastern Mediterranean, Aegean Sea and Black Sea. The trends of these clusters are directly related to the tilt of the chart in the different regions.

²³ Although the chart was not obviously constructed on geographical coordinates, an arbitrary grid was created on the equirectangular projection centered at the 36° N parallel, from which latitudes and longitudes on the chart could be read. The grid was fixed at Punta Tarifa (36.0° N, 5.6° W), where both the latitude and longitude errors are zero.

Figure 7 - Variation of the apparent latitude errors with longitude, in the chart of Mecia de Viladestes (1413), after it was submitted to a clockwise rotation of 8.5°, and the data for the Atlantic were excluded. Notice how the data are grouped in two clusters roughly delimited by the 20° E meridian: the western one, with a clockwise tilt; and the eastern one, with a counterclockwise tilt. Also notice how the eastern cluster is displaced northward by about 0.5°.

Figure 7 illustrates the corresponding variations (with exclusion of the Atlantic), after the chart was submitted to a clockwise rotation of 8.5° to eliminate the average tilt. Here, we can identify another cluster of data with a larger dispersion, comprising the Central Mediterranean and the Adriatic Sea (red and orange circles in the center).²⁴

Another important feature probably never detected is the northward displacement of the eastern Mediterranean, Aegean Sea and Black Sea by about 0.5°. This may represent convincing evidence that two parts, grossly divided by the 20° E meridian, were charted separately and later brought together. In the geographic grid of meridians and parallels that is implicit to the same chart (Fig. 8), signs of what appears to be a stitching line can be seen in two irregularities: the undulations of the parallels in the northwest part of the Aegean Sea, and the smaller distance between adjacent meridians in the south-eastern part of the Gulf of Sirte.²⁵ These are features shared by many other early charts, like the one of Mecia de Viladestes (Fig. 5).

²⁴ As previously noticed by other researchers for a few charts, less obvious subdivisions can be identified using a finer analysis, but such an exercise would be beyond the point I want to make here. See, for example, Loomer (1987, 159) and Nicolai (2014, 269).

²⁵ These two irregularities were also noticed by Nicolai (2014, Ch. 7) on his cartometric analysis of five charts, but the corresponding control points were rejected as outliers.

Figure 8 - Geographical grid of meridians and parallels of the chart of Mecia de Viladestes (1413), estimated from a set of points of known geographical coordinates (yellow diamonds), positively identified in the old chart and in a modern map. Notice the irregularities of the grid in the northwest part of the Aegean Sea and the southeastern margin of the Gulf of Sirte, indicated by two blue rectangles.

A note should be made of an alternative explanation for the lack of homogeneity affecting the charts. While the presence of scale, tilt, and accuracy variations clearly reflects the presence of various sources, it is uncertain whether those sources consisted only in regional charts or also in different *sets of data* used in the compilation. While the presence of stitching marks seems to confirm the first possibility, in what concerns the two parts separated by the 20° E meridian, it does not exclude the second, most especially for the subdivisions identified in the data.

Anyway, the occurrence of those variations excludes the hypothesis that the making of the earliest chart of the whole Mediterranean Sea was based on some kind of organized survey, where common measuring standards for distances and directions were adopted for all regions.

5.3 Roel Nicolai's thesis

As previously noted, Roel Nicolai based his thesis – that the medieval portolan charts were copied from ancient regional maps produced by an older civilization – on the conclusion, drawn from the results of a cartometric analysis, that those charts are too accurate to have been the product of medieval navigation and technology.

As part of his cartometric analysis of five portolan charts, Nicolai concluded, based on the spatial variations of scale and tilt, that they were probably constructed as an assemblage of regional representations. After estimating their number and geographical coverage, he then

proceeded with a planimetric accuracy assessment. The process consisted of numerically adjusting each of the parts to the equiarectangular and the Mercator projections, *after* they were *re-scaled* and *corrected for tilt*, and some control points were rejected as *outliers*, because they did not pass a statistical test of compliance with those projections. The conclusion drawn from the results was that the Mercator projection provided the best fit, and that the planimetric accuracy of the *adjusted parts* was far too high to be explained by the medieval navigational methods (Nicolai, 2014, 201, Fig. 6.9). The circular argument seems obvious, as this conclusion was drawn after the data of each part were manipulated (re-scaled, re-oriented and purged of some control points) in such a way as to better conform to a *Mercator projection*, previously assuming that those components were originally oriented to the geographical North and unaffected by any scale variations. In other words, the object of the analysis performed by Nicolai was not any extant chart of the whole Mediterranean Sea but a set of adjusted regional components. The fallacy of confounding the two should be underlined, especially in the light of his assertion that such an accuracy was beyond the capabilities of medieval technology.

Nicolai also fails to explain in any satisfactory way the scale and tilt variations of the regional parts, as they appear on the original charts, and how the putative Mercator sub-charts were mounted in such a way as to make the tilt of the composite approximately match the average value of magnetic declination in the Mediterranean Sea. In a later justification, he suggested that the partial chart of the Western Mediterranean may have been oriented with the help of an early compass, and the rest of the parts were fitted together using overlaps of common sections of coastline, which might explain the strange regional scale and orientation variations on the final chart (Nicolai, 2016a, 8).

An issue that still needs to be addressed in Nicolai's thesis is the closeness of the Mercator projection to the actual geometry of the portolan charts, once the tilt is removed, which various authors had noticed since, at least, Nordenskjöld (1987, 17). That was the case of Loomer (1987, 166-167), who emphatically stressed that this feature resulted from the navigational data used in their construction, and certainly not from the deliberate use of the projection. In fact, it is easy to demonstrate that a Mercator representation can be *automatically* constructed by simply using enough rhumb line tracks connecting places, a fact apparently overlooked by Nicolai.²⁶

Finally, and concerning the navigational data used by medieval chart makers, Nicolai considers – for the construction of his argument – that in no way could redundant measurements be used to improve the accuracy of the estimated distances between places, because the concept of average value had not yet been introduced at the time. This is a deceptive and anachronistic argument, which implicitly assumes some kind of intellectual

²⁶ See Gaspar (2010, p. 81; 2011, p. 237). It is noteworthy the fact that the Mercator projection was first proposed by Gerard Mercator in his planisphere of 1569 but was only fully adopted in nautical cartography well into the 18th century, after the longitude problem was solved. Its application to mapping in the Middle Ages would necessarily imply that geographical coordinates of some places could be determined by astronomical methods. Even assuming that such an undertaking was within the reach of the hypothetical older civilization postulated by Nicolai, why choose the Mercator projection for mapping small regions in the Mediterranean?

inferiority of the medieval people. Even accepting that the formal concept of average was foreign to medieval cartographers and pilots, improving the planimetric accuracy of the charts was most probably an iterative *graphical* process occurring in the formative period of chart development, not a *numerical* one.²⁷ Clear evidence of that process can be found in the way the depiction of the Italian Peninsula, Adriatic Sea and Atlantic coasts of Europe evolved during the early fourteenth century. Another significant change occurred in the second half of the fifteenth century, when the systematic exploration of the Atlantic coast of Africa led to the enlargement of the geographic coverage of portolan charts. Unless the accuracy of the navigational methods and the skill of cartographers had improved significantly as to match the alleged geodetic standards, which was certainly not the case, this fact adds to the inconsistency of Nicolai's claims about the incapacity of medieval technology. To circumvent this argument, Nicolai recently published a paper postulating that also the cartography of the coast of Africa, produced by the Portuguese in the late fifteenth and early sixteenth century, was based on older maps drawn on the *plate carrée* projection. When and by whom was not specified.²⁸

5.4 Before the chart

For a medieval pilot who had never seen a map and only relied on his own experience at sea and the knowledge transmitted orally to him, looking at a nautical chart for the first time must have been an extraordinary revelation. Not only the paths between ports he had so carefully memorized were there represented faithfully, but also many others he had never practised, across unfamiliar areas, could be easily retrieved from the chart. This would allow him to learn in advance the course and distance to any distant place, as well as to control the position of the ship by comparing the content of the chart with the coastal features and islands he could see along the way. Even when not in sight of land, the position of the ship could be carefully estimated and plotted on the chart from the course steered and the distance made from the last known position. Furthermore, complex and voluminous navigational information could now be stored effectively and accurately, and be easily transmitted to others even if they did not speak his language. Finally, copies of the charts could be made and conveyed to other ships' masters, pilots and apprentices, dramatically enlarging their knowledge and facilitating the learning process.

How realistic is this hypothetical situation, assuming that it took place at the time nautical charts were being disseminated among pilots in the Mediterranean Sea? The answer to this question is more complex than it seems at first sight. Purposedly, it has been assumed that the protagonist of our story had never seen a map. But is this assumption reasonable? Maps, in the form of two-dimensional representations of the Earth's surface, are known to have been made by different civilizations since remote antiquity. During the Middle Ages, depictions of the *ecumene* circulated among educated people. Some, inspired by the TO

²⁷ This was more recently also proposed by Tony Campbell (2021-2023, '1.4c. The rectification procedure').

²⁸ See Nicolai (2021). The fact that the Portuguese charts of the late fifteenth and early sixteenth century were based on various sources of data was first noted and discussed by Gaspar (2010), and then revisited in Gaspar (2012, 191-194) and McIntosh & Gaspar (2021, 167-174). The detailed analysis and conclusions made in these works about the origin of those data, and how they shaped the geometry of the charts, were apparently disregarded by Nicolai.

map of Isidore of Seville, were symbolic and highly stylized representations with an explicit religious content; others, such as Muhammad al-Idrisi's *Tabula Rogeriana*²⁹, were attempts to represent the known world as realistically as possible. Although the protagonist of our story may have been illiterate – as probably were most of the pilots of the time –, he had certainly contact with a milieu of traders, clerics, and other cultivated people, who were certainly acquainted with books and maps. Not only does it seem plausible that the general shape of the Mediterranean Sea was common knowledge by then, but such an information must have been highly appreciated for those who ploughed its waters, both for trade, war, or religious purposes.

An important issue related with this hypothetical situation is how, before the introduction of nautical cartography in Europe, pilots stored the information about their trips, so that it could be recalled when necessary and be taught to others. In a recent essay published online, Campbell (2021-2023) carefully elaborated the argument that the navigational experience of the Mediterranean pilots since antiquity was kept and used as *mental maps*, without any graphical or written support. Campbell based his argument on current scholarship about how various communities, both in land and at sea, have successfully navigated across long distances, only based on the memorized information of previous trips, kept as mental maps. According to his hypothesis, the first European nautical chart was constructed between ca. 1154 and 1205, using the mental maps kept by pilots, which consisted in a network of paths connecting prominent places regularly disposed across the Mediterranean basin. Once this grid was transferred to a piece of parchment, it was then completed with more detailed information about the coastlines and place names, which Campbell (2021-2023, 'C.3. The Mental Map in the Mediterranean Context') considers having also been memorized by the pilots.

Exactly of what consisted those mental maps of pelagic tracks is unclear in Campbell's argument. My interpretation is that they were a collection of paths, each defined by the names of the start and end points, the course and the distance between them, and other pieces of useful information, such as memorized images, navigational hazards, etc. This is what in cognitive science is known as *path knowledge* (which I would essentially classify as *one-dimensional* cognitive representations), as opposed to *survey knowledge* (*two-dimensional* representations). A parallel is made by Campbell with the mental maps kept by the drivers of the London black cabs, who used to go through a long learning process to memorize the names of the streets and the ways across the large city. A relevant question not addressed by Campbell is whether the medieval pilots, as well as the taxi drivers, could infer true two-dimensional representations of the surface *inside their minds*, from the collection of memorized sets of one-dimensional paths intersecting each other.³⁰ In simpler

²⁹ Muhammad al-Idrisi's *Tabula Rogeriana* (or *Book of Roger*) was commissioned by the Norman King of Sicily, Roger II, and completed around 1154. The book is written in Arabic and contains seventy maps covering the world known at the time. Al-Idrisi was certainly influenced by Ptolemy's *Geography*, which had been translated into Arabic by al-Khwarizmi (ca. 780- ca. 850) and al-Battani (ca. 858-929). Such an influence seems clear in the small round representation of the ecumene which accompanied later editions of the book. See Medea-Chart database: <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/atlas/660>, <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/238>.

³⁰ See Campbell (2021-2023, 'B.3b.1. London's Black Cab drivers'). The situation of the taxi drivers cannot, strictly speaking, be taken as equivalent to the one of our medieval pilot because, as Campbell noted, those

words, could our medieval pilot (or even a modern one) estimate the direct course and distance between two places that *were not part of the same path*? As far as I know, this issue has not yet been satisfactorily solved by the cognitive sciences. One thing seems certain though, if we reasonably assume that the brain of a typical medieval sailor worked essentially the same way as our own: that such a transformation could easily be made with a simple sketch, containing the correctly oriented and scaled paths memorized by the pilots. This is hardly an excessive assumption to make, knowing that many human civilizations have resorted to images to express spatial information, more easily and precisely than could be done by words. That is why I find it unrealistic to consider that, for centuries, mariners were unable or unwilling to register navigational data into graphical form. While one may argue that the American *inuit* people or the Australian Aboriginal travellers might not have cultures naturally prone to drawing, that wasn't certainly the case with the European and Arabic peoples of the Mediterranean region.

A second important point in Campbell's hypothesis is that, because pilots were mostly illiterate, they didn't resort to written notes to store navigational information.³¹ Based on the now accepted interpretation that portolanis derived from nautical charts, and not the other way around, Campbell seems to consider that portolanis did not exist before the first nautical charts were created. The problem with this point is that it also rejects any continuity between the old *periploi* and the medieval sailing directions, as if the former had been forgotten during the Early Middle Ages, and re-invented later.³²

All in all, Campbell's hypothesis should be praised for, at least, two original contributions. Firstly, for introducing the concept of mental maps in medieval navigation; and secondly, for underscoring the fact that navigation in the Mediterranean Sea, both coastal and oceanic, was practised since antiquity without the help of nautical charts. Still, his argument was driven too far on some points, forcing unnecessary and improbable assumptions, such as that a complex network of tracks across the whole Mediterranean, essentially defined by numbers and names, could be easily and effectively memorized; that medieval pilots had never seen a map and weren't aware of the overall shape of the Mediterranean Sea, before the emergence of nautical cartography; that the practise of expressing navigational information both textually and graphically had never occurred before that exact time; and that pilots, because they were mostly illiterate, didn't profit from written navigational information, including that contained in portolanis.

My own interpretation about how navigational information was stored and circulated before the emergence of nautical cartography is more flexible. While fully recognizing that coastal pilots navigating in familiar waters mostly relied on their memories and experience,

drivers learned much of their memorized information from maps. The necessity of keeping that information in their minds resulted from the simple fact that a paper map could not be safely consulted with the car in motion. As we know, the limitation has been resolved with the present-day digital maps and GPS systems.

³¹ Campbell (2021-2023). The fact that most pilots were probably illiterate is used many times throughout the text to argue against textual support for navigation. See, for example, 'L.3. Literacy or Illiteracy?'

³² Even if the ancient *periploi* were not used in navigation, as asserted by Campbell (2023, 'C1. Navigation in the Ancient World'), the similarities of organization and content with the medieval portolan suggest that some continuity did exist.

the situation may have often changed with the need to cover larger and poorly known areas, or when the volume and complexity of the information reached a certain limit, beyond which the process may have become unreliable and dangerous. Once again, resorting to notes and sketches must have been a natural process, if not an instinctive urge, for instructed pilots. The advantages of transferring information to a piece of parchment or to the margins of another manuscript, were obvious: not only it would be more safely and accurately stored, but also could be easily passed to others. The idea that illiterate pilots – who were probably the majority – could not embark on such a practise is irrelevant, as they were certainly not the ones resorting to it.

Postulating a precise moment when some pilot or group of pilots decided, *for the first time*, transfer the navigational knowledge they kept in their heads to an animal skin, in the form of a representation of the whole Mediterranean Sea, seems also questionable. More likely, sketches and written notes made by many local pilots must have co-existed for a long time (maybe centuries), before the information was finally gathered and combined: first as regional charts, and after, as global representations of the Mediterranean and Black Seas. What triggered such an evolution can only be speculated, but it may be related to the increase of trade in the Mediterranean, later boosted by the introduction of the magnetic compass in navigation.³³ The very existence of the medieval portolan chart, covering from the Atlantic coasts of Europe and northwest Africa to the Black Sea, demonstrates that the pieces of information necessary to its construction were collected, accumulated, circulated, and became available to those interested in its making. I'm referring not only to the navigational data produced or kept by mariners (local charts, sketches, notes, memorized paths, lists of place names, etc.) but also to that provided by travellers, merchants, scholars, and local officials. The effort and time necessary for such an undertaking must have been considerable, and certainly implied some form of organization. Keeping the more cultivated classes out of this process seems unnatural. Once the potential of nautical charts was recognized by the instructed people associated with trade (ship owners, clerics, nobles, officials, etc.), their involvement was probably natural and inevitable. That was the interpretation of Ramon Pujades, when addressing the historical context in which the medieval nautical cartography was likely born, in a milieu of Italian scholars in contact with maritime trade (Pujades, 2007, 515).

6. Conclusions

From a state of widespread perplexity about the emergence of the medieval nautical chart, which triggered the proposal of disparate theories about their origin, purpose, and method of construction, we have now reached a situation where broad consensuses have been reached around most of the central matters. Campbell's concern about the birth of nautical cartography, underlined in 1987 by his comment that 'among the research problems

³³ As noted above, there is a difficulty here, related to the possible connection between the alleged proto-portolan chart, based on astronomical directions and representing the whole Mediterranean Sea, and the later regional portolan charts, based on compass directions. Rather than considering that the latter evolved naturally from the first, it could well be that they were mostly unrelated processes.

connected with the portolan charts, the question of their origin is perhaps the most intractable' seems outdated. By the time he wrote his influential chapter, theories about a pre-medieval origin were still alive, the navigational purpose of charts was contested, the use of an intentional map projection in their construction had not yet been ruled out, and the explanation about the tilt of portolan charts had not gathered unanimous agreement among researchers.

About thirty-five years later, the medieval origin of portolan charts is now broadly accepted, a meaningful connection between charts and navigation has been established, magnetic declination has been convincingly demonstrated to be the cause of their tilt, and most researchers agree that portolan charts were constructed using navigational data collected by pilots at sea. Having settled some of the basic questions concerning the emergence of the portolan chart, the attention of the historians has now been displaced to the *details*, such as the date of the first prototypes and how exactly they were made. The important information contained in the *Liber de existencia riveriarum*, combined with a closer look into the geometry and content of the medieval charts, have permitted to conclude that the genesis of nautical cartography is a much richer and more complex process than previously envisaged by the historians. Significant examples are the possibility that more than one prototype may have been prepared during the thirteenth century, and that a primitive type of chart based on astronomical directions probably preceded the model of the Carte Pisane. The initial perplexity about the very creation of the portolan chart has given place to some irritating issues, whose clarification doesn't seem to gather unanimous opinions. That is the case with how the information necessary to construct the first charts was stored and circulated, or whether the earliest charts were piecewise assemblages of regional charts or not. An important point to restate is that much of what is now being proposed resorts to educated speculation, as no material or textual evidence clearly supports any of the claims. That is the case of the mental map theory of Tony Campbell, or my own conservative idea that the earliest manifestations of nautical cartography, in the form of simple sketches or loose written notes, may be lost in the mist of the past. My optimistic interpretation is that this is a sign that most of the fundamental doubts of last century have been clarified.

Research conditions have dramatically improved over the last decades, with the introduction of such powerful tools as radiocarbon dating, hyperspectral analysis, geomagnetic models, cartometric methods and numerical modelling. More recently, a significant step forward was taken by migrating the inventories of portolan charts prepared by Tony Campbell, Dick Pfloderer and others to a modern information system, the Medea-Chart database, containing not only basic information about the early charts, such as archival location, size, year of production, etc., but also high-resolution images of most of them. This system, which is available online worldwide, opens promising research perspectives in fundamental aspects directly or indirectly related to the origins problem, such as dating and authorship, chart content, the use of charts in navigation, or the copying methods.

For too long, the history of nautical cartography has been confined to a relatively small niche of historians and specialized publications of modest circulation. From time to time,

usually triggered by some unorthodox theory or a historical celebration, the subject is brought to the attention of the media and reaches the public, in the form of newspaper articles, television series and books. On few of those occasions is the truly remarkable circumstances surrounding the birth and evolution of nautical charts referred to. One of them is the deep involvement of uneducated people – pilots and chart makers – in the genesis of an artefact with such an extraordinary impact on human civilization. Not only did nautical charts dramatically improve the efficacy and safety of navigation, most especially during the maritime expansion of the Europeans, but also, they have provided the necessary information for the first accurate cartographic representations of the world. While these facts are widely known by historians, and are often recalled, it has taken a long time before the inner secrets of the old charts began to be unveiled. One of the reasons is the small number of historians solely dedicated to the subject; a different one is the need to dive into the geometrical intricacies of the old charts in order to fully understand how they were made and used in navigation.

Some authors before me have expressed a wish to see the history of cartography included within the broader scope of the history of science. This could raise the attention of a larger audience and attract the interest of a new generation of researchers, equipped with broader intellectual and scientific tools. That is also my desire.

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